

Coumarins from *Pimpinella monoica*

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The seeds of the plant *Pimpinella monoica* (Family : Umbelliferae) have been examined by us and two coumarins have been isolated and identified.

A concentrated benzene extract of the powdered seeds of *P. monoica* on chromatography over a column of silica gel furnished two coumarins having m.p. 188–89° and 151–52° respectively. The former compound has the molecular formula $C_{12}H_8O_4$. It showed absorption maxima at 221 (log ϵ 4.40), 242 (sh), 248 (log ϵ 4.20), 258 (log ϵ 4.17), 267 (log ϵ 4.20) and 308 (log ϵ 4.18) $m\mu$. The λ max values agreed well with those reported^{1,2} for bergapten but some discrepancy was observed in the ϵ max values. The U.V. spectrum recorded with an authentic sample of bergapten, however, agreed well with that of our compound. The identity of this coumarin with bergapten was finally established by direct comparison (mixed m.p., I.R. and U.V.).

The second coumarin (m.p. 151–52°) has the molecular formula $C_{13}H_{10}O_5$ (M^+ 246). It showed absorption maxima at 221, 245, 270 and 312.5 $m\mu$ in the U.V. spectrum. Its N.M.R. spectrum ($CDCl_3$, 60 Mc) showed a sharp singlet at 4.12 δ (6H) for two methoxy groups ($-OCH_3$). Two doublets centered at 6.2 (1H, $J = 10$ c.p.s.) and 8.06 (1H, $J = 10$ c.p.s.) δ were attributed to the unsubstituted C-3 and C-4 protons respectively of the coumarin nucleus. Such downfield shift³ of the C-4 proton, which is characteristic of 5-alkoxy substituted psoralen, a linear furano-coumarin, indicated the presence of a similar system in the second coumarin. This was further corroborated by the presence of two doublets centred at 7.58 ($J = 2.5$ c.p.s.) and 6.96 ($J = 2.5$ c.p.s.) δ corresponding to the α - and β -protons of the furan ring. This coumarin was finally identified as isopimpinellin (5-methoxy psoralen) by direct comparison (mixed m.p., I.R. and U.V. spectra) with an authentic sample. The seeds contain still another coumarin in small amount which is being further studied.

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1. A. G. Caldwell and E. R. H. Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 541.
2. D. P. Chakraborty and S. K. Chakraborti, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1961, **24**, 17.
3. J. F. Fisher and H. E. Nordby, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, **22**, 1489.

